

Positive and negative directions of globalization in ensuring sustainable development

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Abstract: The article represents a method of in-depth analysis of a topic, its importance, program, or achievements using a purpose-oriented reading strategy. The topic of development usually focuses on the study of advancements and improvements in various fields such as economic, social, technological and intellectual growth.

Key words: economic, social progress, development

Enter. Progress is a form of development from simple to complex, from bottom to top, its rise. In the literature, development is often equated with development, in fact, it is a direction of the philosophy of development. Also, in some literature, development is used only in the sense of social development in society, which is also a one-sided approach. Development is used in philosophical literature as progressive development. Usually there are 2 important directions of development, one is progress (progressive development) and the other is crisis (regressive development). The mistake of applying progress only to society is that progress also occurs in systems outside of society. For example, the development of certain living organisms, the development of a disease in a patient, the development of a chemical process, etc. Progress is relative.

Development can be progress for one system and regression for another. For example, the development of a disease is a crisis (regression) for the patient's body, if it is progress for the viruses that cause the disease. Any system experiences both progress and crisis during its development. The prosperity of the system means progress, and its decay means crisis. Development is a natural and necessary process characteristic of both inanimate and inorganic nature, animate and organic nature, society, human thinking and psyche.

Development takes place in the micro, macro, and mega world. Thanks to development, the world is perfected and improved, it takes place in the form of the processes of emergence, complication, growth, renewal, recovery, system formation. Development is a holistic process.

Sustainability is about meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This concept aims to ensure that living conditions and resources in society are able to meet human needs, but without compromising the integrity of our planet.

Key Printers to Ensure Progress:

1. Environmental Protection:

This means rational management of natural resources, reduction of harmful waste and preservation of biodiversity.

2. Economic Stability:

Economic development is necessary, but this process must be done in a way that does not harm the environment and helps reduce poverty.

3. Social Justice:

All citizens should be guaranteed equal rights to basic social services such as education, health and employment.

4. Technological Achievements:

It is necessary to produce new, sustainable technologies and create solutions that can be used in the long term.

UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

1. Poverty Eradication:

End all forms of poverty worldwide.

2. Improving Food Security and Nutrition:

End hunger, achieve food security and promote improved nutrition.

3. Environmental Protection:

Taking measures to protect the environment in order to protect our land.

BTM is a global challenge to achieve a sustainable future. With these goals, we strive to reduce global poverty, protect the planet, and provide people with a better, more sustainable future.

The Sustainable Development Goals are a global call of the United Nations aimed at improving the way of life and well-being of all mankind by improving the economic, social and environmental situation in the world, and building a fair and stable society. Since the experience of different countries in the field of sustainable development is very different, all the goals and related tasks of the 2030 Agenda are formulated in a general, universal form and, as a rule, there are no specific quantitative goals. It is determined that each country will localize the BRM, that is, develop national development goals based on its development priorities and financial capabilities from the 169 tasks of the 2030 agenda. Countries should adapt these targets to their national circumstances, define quantitative indicators for the relevant statistical indicators for each objective, and define objectives and specific quantitative indicators in national strategic documents.

Today, at the United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs (UNDESA), the Division on Sustainable Development Goals (DSDG) focuses on SDGs and related thematic issues, including water, energy, climate, oceans, urbanization, transport, science and technology. provides support and capacity building activities.

Nowadays, the world is undergoing a process of globalization, which is gradually changing, which is increasingly taking the world of humanity closer and deeper into their lives, affecting their national culture and spirituality. As a result of this process, a clash of different civilizations and cultures took place, causing a number of problems and causing threats to the spirituality of nations. President Islam Karimov, who clearly understood the positive and negative nature of this process, in the third chapter of his works entitled "High Spirituality-Invincible Power" published this year by "Manaviyat" publishing house, focused on the example of "globalization processes and spiritual threats". In this work, the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan approaches the phenomenon of

globalization as follows, "this process represents the formation of a completely new economic, social-political, natural-biological global environment and, at the same time, the transformation of existing national and regional problems into global problems" expressed few opinions and explained the essence of the issue in detail. Let's find out what the word globalization is, or rather, its basic dictionary meaning. The term "Global" means global-"common" in French, and globe-"sphere" in Latin. Thus, globalization can be interpreted as an "all-encompassing" term. The emergence of global problems led to the formation of concepts of globalization. Even as a result of this process, science-globalization (global studies), which focuses on universal human problems, was born. Environmental, economic, social and political problems are at the center of this science.

"Another peculiar aspect of the globalization process is that, in the current conditions, it has become a very sharp weapon of ideological influence, and any sane person can certainly observe that it serves the interests of various political forces and centers." The national ideal and ideology of each country is of particular importance in the development of this immunity. Of course, in this, the ideology is based on feelings of love, loyalty, and trust for the motherland, peace and tranquility, which is the age-old dream of our ancestors, to preserve and strengthen it, and to ensure that our traditions, values, and traditions, which have been going on for centuries, will reach future generations. Only when it is built, ideological immunity emerges.

Positive aspects of globalization:

The struggle of the peoples of the world for peace, the cooperation of different countries in economy, politics, science and technology, culture, education and other fields, the fight against the arms race, the fight against drug addiction; unbiased assistance from other countries to the population affected by natural disasters, such as earthquakes, floods, fires, volcanic eruptions, tsunamis, etc.

Disadvantages of Globalization:

Environmental problems, i.e. ozone holes, increase in earth temperature, reduction of forests, i.e. emergence of deserts and deserts, tragedy of the Aral Sea, etc.,

increase in drug addiction, threat to public morale. the expansion of arms and drug trafficking, etc.

References

1. Myself. The first volume. Tashkent, 2000
2. Karimov I.A. Uzbekistan: National conquest, history, politics, ideology. T., 1993, p. 78.
3. Karimov I.A. A book that glorifies good thoughts, good words and good deeds. Nutl at the opening ceremony of the memorial complex dedicated to the 2700th anniversary of the book "Avesta". "Uzbskistoi literature and art" newspaper. November 9, 2001.
4. J. Mustafaev. Social aspects of ideological and ideological upbringing of young people. Proceedings of the Republican scientific-practical conference on the role, role and importance of spiritual heritage in the current globalization. Samarkand. SamISI. 2020. May 20. 306 pages
5. J. Mustafaev. Electronic business and its problems of forming a digital economy in society. Republican scientific conference on "Success in spiritual heritage and its role in 21st century education". May 20, 2021. Samarkand.